

The Effect of Lactonic Ring on the Colour of Azo-dyes.

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Sen and Chakravarti (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2428) prepared some azo-methine, pyronine and triphenylmethane dyes containing a lactonic ring and discussed the influence of the lactone. In order to study the auxochromic or the hypsochromic effect of a lactonic ring, a series of azo-dyes with a lactone ring has now been prepared.

The azo-dyes studied have been prepared in two different ways: *viz.*, by diazotising aryl amines and coupling them with coumarin in an alkaline solution (*cf.* Borsche, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 4116; Hewitt and Mitchell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 1229; 1906, 89, 15; 1906, 89, 17), and by diazotising 6-aminocoumarin and coupling it with different phenols and also with various coumarin derivatives in an alkaline solution.

For a comparative study, the benzene- and naphthalene-azo-coumarins and the benzene- and naphthalene-azocoumaric acids (for preparation of these compounds see Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 391) have been very useful. It has been found that in the azo-coumaric acid derivatives, the affinities of the compounds for the fibres are much greater than those of the azo-coumarin derivatives.

Benzeneazo-*o*-coumaric acid.

Benzeneazocoumarin.

This shows that the auxochromic effect of the free hydroxyl group in the coumaric acid derivatives appreciably diminishes in the coumarin derivatives, where the hydroxyl group is masked, so to say, by the closure of the lactone ring. Although the dyeing properties of the lactones are much less, it is noteworthy that the

depth of colour of the lactone and the corresponding *ortho*-coumaric acid is much the same ; the lactonic ring behaving in this respect just like a hydroxyl group. The following table compares the properties of these two series of compounds.

Name.	Colour.	Shade on silk and wool.	Name.	Colour.	Shade on silk and wool.
1. Benzeneazo-coumarin.	Brownish-yellow	Light yellow	1. Benzene-azo- <i>o</i> -coumaric acid	Yellow	Bright yellow.
2. <i>m</i> -Nitrobenzeneazo-coumarin.	Brownish-yellow	Pale yellow	2. <i>m</i> -Nitrobenzeneazo- <i>o</i> -coumaric acid.	Deep yellow	Brilliant yellow
3. <i>o</i> -Nitrobenzeneazo-coumarin.	Yellow	Dull yellow	3. <i>o</i> -Nitrobenzeneazo- <i>o</i> -coumaric acid	Reddish-yellow	Yellow
4. <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzeneazo-coumarin.	Red	Pale yellow	4. <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzeneazo- <i>o</i> -coumaric acid	Brick red.	Yellowish-red
5. Diphenyl-bis-azo-di-coumarin.	Yellow	Yellow	5. Diphenyl-bisazodi- <i>o</i> -coumaric acid	Yellow	Yellow with slight orange tinge
6. Naphthalene- α -azocoumarin.	Brown	Yellow	6. Naphthalene- α -azocoumaric acid	Greenish-yellow	Bright yellow
7. Naphthalene- β -azocoumarin.	Yellow	Slightly yellowish tinge	7. Naphthalene- β -azocoumaric acid.	Yellow	Yellow
8. Benzene-azo-4 : 6-dimethylcoumarin	Orange	Very faint yellowish tinge	8. Benzeneazo- β : 5-dimethyl- <i>o</i> -coumaric acid.	Chocolate	Yellow

The influence of the lactonic ring on the depth of colour and dyeing property is shown clearly by a comparative study of the following three compounds:—(1) Azocoumarin (2) coumarinazo-coumaric acid, (3) azocoumaric acid. (*cf.* Sen and Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 247).

Azocoumarin,

Coumarinazo-*o*-coumaric acid.

Azo-*o*-coumaric acid.

Of these azocoumaric acid (reddish-brown), in which two hydroxyl groups exert auxochromic effect, dyes reddish-brown shade, the coumarinazocoumaric acid (light brown) containing one lactonic ring and one hydroxyl group a yellow shade and azocoumarin, in which there are two lactonic rings, produces a faint yellowish tinge on the fibres. When dissolved in caustic alkali all of them give a red solution.

Dimethylazocoumarins, though they contain two lactonic rings have little affinity for the fibres, coumarinazo-4:6-dimethylcoumarin (golden yellow) and coumarinazo-4:7-dimethylcoumarin (greenish-yellow) producing only a dull yellow tinge on silk. It has not been possible to break up the lactones and isolate the free acids in these cases for the sake of comparison.

Coumarinazo-4-methyl- α -naphthacoumarin (orange) produces an orange shade on silk and wool probably due to the presence of the naphthalene nucleus.

By introducing an additional hydroxyl group into the azocoumarin molecule as in coumarinazo-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, the colour of the compound deepens to red and the shades on silk and wool are also deepened to reddish-brown. This compound is very similar in colour to coumarinazoresorcinol (red) which also produces a red shade on silk and wool.

Coumarinazo-7:8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (grey) have a polygenetic property producing different shades on mordanted wool.

Coumarinazodimethylaniline produces a faint yellow colour in alkaline solution and a violet colour in acid solution, the sharp change of colour being very suitable for an indicator.

It is interesting to note that 6-iodocoumarin and 6-aldehydocoumarin couples with a diazotised amine to form a free acid and not a lactone. In these cases coupling takes place in the 8-position and it is probable that the acids isolated are the quinonoid forms of the *o*-hydroxyazocompounds according to the hypothesis of Hewitt

(*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 225). Thus diazotised, *p*-nitroaniline forms with 6-iodocoumarin, the free acid, thus:

It is always noticed that the yield of the azo-compounds is not satisfactory when the coupling takes place in the 8-position. Incidentally it may also be mentioned that 6-nitrocoumarin does not form an azo-dye due to the inhibiting action of the nitro-group and that attempts to couple diazotised aminocoumarin with an alkaline solution of aminocoumarin itself are unsuccessful.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Modified Method for the Preparation of 6-Aminocoumarin.—Morgan and Micklethwaits' method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1230) has been found to give poor yields. It has been modified as follows: 6-Nitrocoumarin (10 g.) (readily obtained in a very pure form melting at 185° by crystallising from a small quantity of pyridine) is dissolved in boiling rectified spirit (250 c.c.) in a 500 c.c. flask with an upright condenser and iron filings (20 g.) are added to it. Concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) is slowly added drop by drop to the boiling alcoholic solution with occasional shaking and the heating continued for about two hours. The alcohol is then distilled off and the solution, diluted with water acidified with hydrochloric acid, is filtered off from the unchanged iron filings and nitrocoumarin, and made alkaline with sodium bicarbonate, when a voluminous greenish-yellow precipitate separates out. The precipitate is collected and crystallised from a large volume of boiling water, when long yellow needles separate out. By this method about 7 g. of pure 6-aminocoumarin, m.p. 167° are obtained.

Azocoumarin.—6-Aminocoumarin (2 g.) is dissolved in sulphuric acid (5 c.c. conc. sulphuric acid in 50 c.c. water) and a solution of sodium nitrite (1 g. in 6 c.c. water) is added all at once to prevent the formation of diazoamino compound.

The diazotised solution is then added to an alkaline solution of coumarin (1.8 g.) and after keeping overnight, the solution is acidified with hydrochloric acid and the precipitate dried and crystallised from nitrobenzene or a mixture of nitrobenzene and pyridine (3:1) in beautiful yellow needles which do not melt up to 300°. It dissolves in caustic alkalis and in concentrated sulphuric acid with a red solution. It is almost insoluble in the ordinary organic solvents. (Found: N, 8.5. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.8 per cent.).

Coumarinazo-o-coumaric acid is prepared by coupling diazotised 6-aminocoumarin with an alkaline solution of *o*-coumaric acid in the usual manner. It is purified by desolving in sodium carbonate, reprecipitating with acid and finally crystallising from boiling rectified spirit. It is a light-brown substance decomposing at 177° and its solutions in caustic alkalis and in concentrated sulphuric acid are red in colour. Its colour changes to red when in contact with hydrochloric acid. (Found: N, 8.1. $C_{18}H_{12}O_5N_2$ requires N, 8.3 per cent.).

Azo-o-coumaric Acid.—A solution of azocoumarin (1 g.) in caustic potash (1 g. in 10 c.c. water) is diluted with water (150 c.c.) and boiled for about an hour with powdered yellow mercuric oxide (2 g.) (cf. Sen and Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 247). The cold solution, filtered from the mercuric oxide, is acidified with hydrochloric acid and the precipitate dissolved in ammonia. The ammoniacal solution is acidified and the precipitate dried and crystallised from dilute alcohol in reddish-brown needles, which do not melt up to 300°. It dissolves in caustic alkalis forming a dull red solution and in concentrated sulphuric acid with a deep red solution. Its colour changes to light violet with the addition of hydrochloric acid. (Found: N, 7.6. $C_{18}H_{14}O_6N_2$ requires N, 7.9 per cent.).

Coumarinazo-4:7-dimethylcoumarin prepared by coupling diazotised 6-aminocoumarin with an alkaline solution of 4:7-dimethylcoumarin, is obtained as a microcrystalline greenish-yellow substance from nitrobenzene, melting at 280°. It is insoluble in the ordinary organic solvents and dissolves in caustic alkalis and in concentrated sulphuric acid with a red solution. (Found: N, 8.3. $C_{20}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.09 per cent.).

Coumarinazo-4:6-dimethylcoumarin obtained by coupling diazotised aminocoumarin with an alkaline solution of 4:6-dimethylcoumarin, crystallises as golden-yellow needles from pyridine, m.p. 262°. It is insoluble in the ordinary organic solvents and forms a

deep red solution in caustic alkalis and in concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: N, 8.1. $C_{20}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.09 per cent.).

Coumarinazo-4-methyl- α -naphthacoumarin prepared by coupling diazotised 6-aminocoumarin with an alkaline solution of α -naphthamethylcoumarin, crystallises in orange needles which do not melt up to 280° , from a large volume of pyridine. It dissolves in caustic alkalis and in concentrated sulphuric acid forming a deep violet solution. It is insoluble in the ordinary organic solvents. (Found: N, 7.73. $C_{23}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires N, 7.33 per cent.).

Coumarinazo-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin prepared by coupling diazotised 6-aminocoumarin with an alkaline solution of β -methylumbelliferone, is a microcrystalline powder from glacial acetic acid, softening at 205° . It dissolves in caustic alkalis and in concentrated sulphuric acid forming a deep red solution. (Found: N, 8.31. $C_{19}H_{12}O_5N_2$ requires N, 8.04 per cent.).

Coumarinazo-7:8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin is prepared by coupling diazotised 6-aminocoumarin with an alkaline solution of β -methyldaphnetin. The deep red solution, on acidification with hydrochloric acid, gives a brownish black precipitate, which is dried in the vacuum desiccator, dissolved in pyridine and poured into toluene. It is a grey substance softening at 282° . It dissolves in caustic alkalis and in concentrated sulphuric acid forming a dark red solution. (Found: N, 7.4. $C_{19}H_{12}O_6N_2$ requires N, 7.7 per cent.).

Coumarinazoresorcinol is prepared from diazotised 6-aminocoumarin and resorcinol. It is a reddish-brown substance melting at 245° , dissolving in caustic alkalis and in concentrated sulphuric acid with a deep red colour. (Found: N, 9.8. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4N_2$ requires N, 9.92 per cent.).

Coumarinazodimethylaniline.—Dimethylaniline (1.5 g.) in hydrochloric acid solution is slowly added to diazotised solution of 6-aminocoumarin (2 g.) and the solution on keeping overnight is made alkaline with ammonia and distilled in steam. The precipitate is filtered off, dissolved in alcohol and poured into water. It is finally crystallised in beautiful plates melting at 231° from absolute alcohol containing a few drops of nitrobenzene. It is a reddish-yellow substance soluble in alkalis with a yellow colour and in acids with a violet colour. It seems to be a good indicator, the change of colour being very sharp. (Found: N, 14.55. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2N_3$ requires N, 14.3 per cent.)

The Azo-compound of p-Nitroaniline with 6-Iodocoumarin.—It is obtained by coupling diazotised p-nitroaniline with an alkaline

solution of 6-iodocoumarin. It is purified by dissolving in ammonia and precipitating with acetic acid. A reddish-brown solid freely soluble in sodium carbonate and bicarbonate solutions. (Found: N, 9.9. $C_{15}H_{10}O_5N_3I$ requires N, 9.57 per cent.).

The *azo-compound* of 6-aminocoumarin with 6-iodocoumarin is purified by dissolving in sodium bicarbonate and reprecipitating with acetic acid. The solution and precipitation are repeated several times and the precipitate dried, dissolved in alcohol and poured into water. Brown powder, freely soluble in sodium bicarbonate solution with effervescence. (Found: N, 5.88. $C_{18}H_{11}O_5N_2I$ requires N, 6.06 per cent.).

The *azo-compound* of 6-aminocoumarin with 6-aldehydocoumarin is prepared in the usual manner and purified by dissolving in ammonia and reprecipitating with acetic acid. It is a brown powder insoluble in alcohol and soluble in sodium bicarbonate. (Found: N, 7.2. $C_{19}H_{12}O_6N_2$ requires N, 7.7 per cent.).

p-Nitrobenzeneazo-7:8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin is prepared by coupling diazotised *p*-nitroaniline with an alkaline solution of β -methyldaphnetin. It is obtained in the pure state as a reddish-brown powder softening at 292° by pouring its solution in pyridine into toluene. (Found: N, 12.02. $C_{16}H_{11}O_6N_3$ requires N, 12.3 per cent.).

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